

ISic2884

I.Sicily inscription 2884

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 14217

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334885

1. Piero

2. Macilia vi-

3. ro d(—

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645277

PHI 334885

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 777

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprietà Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.111 pl.135

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2884. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387609>